

Inter-EURLs Working Group on NGS (Next Generation Sequencing)

Foreword

The Working Group (WG) has been established by the European Commission with the aim to promote the use of NGS across the EURLs' networks, build NGS capacity within the EU and ensure liaison with the work of the EURLs and the work of EFSA and ECDC on the NGS mandate sent by the Commission. The WG includes all the EURLs operating in the field of the microbiological contamination of food and feed and this document represents a deliverable of the WG and is meant to be diffused to all the respective networks of NRLs.

Guidelines for the validation of Whole Genome Sequencing for accreditation

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1. Introduction

According to Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2025/179 (1), Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) shall be performed on isolates of food-borne pathogens associated with food-borne outbreaks. For this, National Reference Laboratories and/or Official Laboratories shall be accredited for this method according to EN ISO/IEC 17025:2017 (1).

To enable National Accreditation Bodies to assess laboratories in a harmonised way, European Accreditation has published a Guideline for the Accreditation of Laboratories carrying out Genetic Testing using Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) Techniques (EA 4/24- G: 2025) (3).

The present document produced by the Inter EURLs WG for NGS **does not replace** the procedures of the Quality Assurance Systems in use in the accredited laboratories, but it is meant to be used alongside, with the aim of giving reference to internationally recognized rules and procedures acknowledged by standards, where available, or other documents that can be used for the technical validation of the WGS workflow.

This document considers all steps of the workflow, including both wet lab and dry lab, but does not comprise the accreditation of the cluster analysis as this guidance document is meant to facilitate the accreditation of WGS workflow to respond to the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2025/179 (produce data and send to EFSA) (1).

For additional information and specific requests regarding the different pathogens, the specific EURLs can be contacted at the following addresses:

- EURL for *Campylobacter*: eurl-campylobacter@sva.se
- EURL for *Escherichia coli*: crl.vtec@iss.it
- EURL for *Listeria monocytogenes*: eurl-listeria@anses.fr
- EURL for *Salmonella*: EURLSalmonella@rivm.nl

2. Scope and Field of application

This supporting document aims at providing guidance on the process of accreditation of WGS and indicates the parameters to be considered for the validation of bioinformatics, including the criteria for the acceptance of test results. In this document “WGS of the foodborne bacteria” are those obtained with the microorganisms concerned by the EU implementing regulation (EU) 2025/179 (1), namely *Campylobacter coli* and *C. jejuni*, *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Salmonella enterica*. As for *E. coli*, this guideline will be focused on Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*.

As the validation of WGS is already in the scope of international standards, explicit reference is made to those documents, while additional information specific to the organisms in the scope of this document is provided.

3. Definitions

Accuracy: closeness of agreement between a test result and reference value.

Metadata: descriptive data associated with the sequenced isolate.

Reference data: well characterized reference genomes or datasets.

Repeatability: closeness of agreement between independent test results obtained with the same method on identical test items in the same laboratory by the same operator in the same run using the same equipment within short intervals of time (in case of bioinformatics analysis: ability to obtain identical results with the same pipeline on the same data series in the same computational environment).

Reproducibility: closeness of agreement between independent test results obtained with the same method on identical test items in different conditions, such as in different laboratories, by different operators, with different instruments or in different sequencing runs (in case of bioinformatics analysis: ability to obtain consistent results in different computational environments).

Sensitivity: ability of an analytical method to correctly identify the presence of a target analyte, expressed as the proportion of true positive results obtained from samples known to contain the analyte. $Se = (\text{Number of positive results found} / \text{total number of expected positive isolates}) \times 100\%$

Specificity: ability of a molecular method to correctly identify the absence of the target analyte, expressed as the proportion of true negative results obtained from samples known not to contain the target. $Sp = (\text{Number of negative results found} / \text{total number of expected negative isolates}) \times 100\%$

WGS workflow: ordered set of analytical procedures executed starting from a bacterial culture and including DNA sequencing and bioinformatics analysis to obtain interpretable results.

Pipeline: ordered set of computational tools, algorithms, and data-processing steps that are executed in a defined sequence to transform raw data into interpretable and reproducible results.

4. Specifications for accreditation of the WGS workflow

The WGS workflow includes two main steps: a “wet” laboratory part, which includes all the analytical steps needed to produce raw sequencing data, and a “dry” laboratory part, which consists in deciphering the raw sequencing files to obtain interpretable results by applying bioinformatics pipelines. These two steps require different validation procedures, which will be dealt with separately in the following sections.

4.1 Producing WGS data

- Bacterial Manipulation: EN ISO 23418:2022 (4)
- DNA Isolation: EN ISO 23418:2022 criteria and controls in Table 1 (4)
- Library preparation: Primary EN ISO 23418:2022 criteria and controls in Table 1 (4); Secondary ISO 20397-2:2021 (5)
- Sequencing process: Primary EN ISO 23418:2022 (4); Secondary ISO 20397-2:2021 (5)
- Data quality metrics: ISO 20397-2:2021 (5)

For more detailed information about validation of the WGS workflow, clause 10 (Table 4) of EN ISO 23418:2022 (4) should be consulted. Table 1 is an example of how Table 4 of ISO EN 23418:2022 can be interpreted.

The parameters to be determined in the validation study shall be:

- Repeatability (accuracy/precision) = (number of within-run replicates in agreement) / (total # within-run replicates) x 100%
- Reproducibility (accuracy/precision) = (number of between-run replicates in agreement) / (total # between-run replicates) x 100%
- Agreement with other methods (accuracy/trueness) = [Number of correct results (positive and negative) / total number of samples] x 100%.

It is important to cover a range of target organisms representative of the scope of the intended validation. The number of strains used for testing repeatability and reproducibility can be smaller than that of testing agreement with other methods. When testing agreement with other methods it is important to cover a representative subset of relevant target characteristics. Annex 1 lists examples of relevant determinants for the organisms included in the scope of the document. The EURLs can provide strains for the validation, upon request by contacting the EURL for the specific pathogen.

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Table 1. An interpretation of validation of workflow stages as illustrated in Table 4 of ISO 23418:2022.

Step	Validation stage	Repeatability	Reproducibility	Agreement with other methods
1	Pure culture	Include cultures prepared on same day by operator 1. Use strain collection A ¹ .	Include cultures prepared on different days ³ by operator 2 ⁴ . Use strain collection A ¹ .	Include strains with different characteristics. Use strain collection A+B ² .
2	DNA extraction	Include DNA extractions produced in triplicate from same culture (step 1) prepared on same day by operator 1, using the same batches of reagents.	Include DNA extractions prepared from cultures (step 1) on different days ³ by operator 2 ⁴ , using different batches of reagents.	Include DNA extractions prepared from cultures (step 1) from strains with different characteristics.
3	DNA sequencing	Include libraries prepared from DNA extractions (step 2) by operator 1 on the same day and (if possible) in the same run.	Include libraries prepared from DNA extractions (step 2) by operator 2 ⁴ on different days ³ in different runs ³ of the same instrument, and on different instruments if relevant.	Include libraries prepared from DNA extractions (step 2) from strains with different characteristics.

¹Strain collection A: A subset of strains representative of the scope of the validation (less than 10 strains, considering the maximum sequencing capacity in one run).

²Strain collection B: A subset of strains representative of different characteristics of the target organisms of the scope of the validation.

³On any day, except when operator 1 is doing step 1, 2 or 3, respectively for each step.

⁴The number of operators depends on routines of the laboratory.

4.2 Acceptance criteria for producing WGS data

QC thresholds for each target species are detailed in Table 1 of the Inter EURL WG document “Guidelines for Dry-Lab Quality Control Metrics and Acceptance Thresholds in Short-Read WGS of zoonotic and indicator bacteria” (Deliverable 10, Clause 5, available at this [link](#)).

The following QC parameters can be determined (examples of acceptance criteria are available in Table 1 of Deliverable 10 or Table A.2 of EN ISO 23418:2022) to evaluate repeatability and reproducibility:

- minimum read depth
- base quality score
- genome size
- GC content
- level of contamination
- percentage of missing cgMLST loci
- identification of relevant targets (see below)

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The accuracy of the method compared to other methods is determined by examining how well the sequences generated match relevant target characteristics (e.g. species, ST, virulence genes, and AMR genes) and group or exclude strains based on genetic relatedness, compared to the expected results. As reference method, a method with a different underlying chemistry or technology can be used to exclude method-specific artifacts. The choice of reference method depends on the type of variant to be validated and may include Sanger sequencing, real-time PCR (qPCR) or digital PCR (dPCR), and results from an inter-laboratory study or proficiency tests. Examples of target characteristics and acceptance criteria are presented for each target species in Annex 1.

Data that pass QC thresholds (Table 1, Deliverable 10) should produce a repeatability and reproducibility of 100% and at least 90-95% agreement with other methods to be accepted. Data from occasional strains not fulfilling these criteria should be discarded and sequencing should be repeated. If the issue appears for more than occasional strains, the laboratory needs to perform a Root Cause Analysis.

4.3 Bioinformatic analyses of WGS data

Refer to EN ISO 23418:2022 Table 4 (4) for an overview of the procedure for validating the pipelines.

According to EN ISO 23418, the validation parameters to be determined shall be:

- **Repeatability** (accuracy/precision): identical results should be obtained from the same data set by repeating the analysis on the same infrastructure, using the same version of the software and the same parameters. $\text{Repeatability} = (\text{number of results obtained from same-infrastructure analysis in agreement}) / (\text{total number of analyses repeated on the same infrastructure}) \times 100\%$
- **Reproducibility** (accuracy/precision): consistent results should be obtained by analysing the same dataset in a different computational environment (e.g. different computer or computing cluster or supercomputing node), using the same version of the software and the same parameters. $\text{Reproducibility} = (\text{number of results obtained from different computational environment analysis in agreement}) / (\text{total number of analyses repeated on a different infrastructure}) \times 100\%$
- **Agreement with other methods** (accuracy/trueness): comparable results should be obtained by analysing the same dataset with a different pipeline developed for the same application. $\text{Agreement with other methods} = [\text{Number of correct results (positive and negative)} / \text{total number of samples}] \times 100\%$.

The validation of the bioinformatic analysis should be supplemented with external datasets to demonstrate that the analysis performs reliably across a wide spectrum of variants and genomic complexities. This provides a higher level of statistical confidence than can be achieved solely through the internally generated validation samples (from the wet laboratory part).

EN ISO 23418:2022 (4) does not give information on the number of strains to be tested. EN ISO 16140-7 (7) describes a protocol for the validation of identification methods but may be less applicable for validation of the WGS workflow. On the other hand, EN ISO 16140-7 does give information on the number of strains to be tested for a validation study. Hence, it may be worthwhile to combine the information of both ISO documents for validation of the WGS bioinformatic workflow. According to EN ISO 16140-7 the number of strains to be tested at species level is (at least) 25 strains per species. For this it may be advisable to select different strains from the most important/most frequently found serogroups/serovars/types per species.

Reference Data shall be used for validating the pipelines. These include WGS of well characterized reference strains with known features. For example, for Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* this can include five genomes per serogroup and gene feature.

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In case a commercial software for the bioinformatic analysis is validated for the accreditation purpose, the reference data can be available from the developer and/or the distributor of the pipeline.

For in-house developed pipelines, the EURLs can provide data and/or strains for the validation. Data available is described in the Inter EURL WG document “Reference Whole Genome Sequencing collection” (Deliverable 2, available at this [link](#)) and additional data can be made available upon request by contacting the EURL for the specific pathogen.

If the pipeline is used as alternative method for a reference method, e.g. as alternative method for serotyping of *Salmonella*, then the validation shall be performed in accordance with ISO 16140-6:2019 (6). For in-house validation, only the method comparison study described in clause 6 of ISO 16140-6:2019 (6) has to be followed.

For the quality parameters to be checked to validate the pipeline, refer to Table 1 of the Inter EURL WG document “Guidelines for Dry-Lab Quality Control Metrics and Acceptance Thresholds in Short-Read WGS of zoonotic and indicator bacteria” (Deliverable 10, Clause 5, available at this [link](#)).

4.4 Acceptance criteria for bioinformatic pipeline validation

The following acceptance criteria are applied to the validation of all data types (characterization data + cgMLST strings production):

Repeatability 100%

Reproducibility 100%

Agreement with other methods (Accuracy/trueness) 90-95%

Sensitivity and specificity shall be determined for the validation of the strains characterization results.

The acceptance criteria are specific for the different species. Tables with the criteria suggested by the respective EURLs are in Annex 1.

Even though the cluster analysis is not in the scope of this document, the laboratory may want to validate this process by referring to ISO 23418:2022 Table 4 (3), using data with known evolutionary relationships (e.g. five genomes related + five unrelated) OR, where not available, by comparing the results obtained with other pipelines with the same scope (e.g. EFSA WGS pipeline, available for download and setup at this [link](#)).

5. Metadata

Metadata are integral to the process of outbreak investigation as are the WGS data.

As a matter of fact, it is specified in the FAQ 6 appended to the EU implementing regulation 2025/179: “A genetic match of WGS profiles between a human isolate and a food isolate alone does not confirm the food as the outbreak source” (1). The clusters identified shall be further investigated, by assessing the sequences metadata.

Although the metadata collection is out of the scope of this supporting document, metadata harmonization is pivotal to make a sense of the whole process and thus it is strongly recommended to refer to the EN ISO 23418:2022 (4) for standardization of the ontologies.

6. References

- 1) Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2025/179 of 31 January 2025 on the collection and transmission of molecular analytical data within the frame of epidemiological investigations of foodborne outbreaks in accordance with Directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (available at this [link](#))
- 2) ISO/IEC 17025:2017. General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories
- 3) EA-4/24 G:2025 Guideline for the Accreditation of Laboratories carrying out Genetic Testing using Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) Techniques ([link](#))
- 4) ISO 23418:2022. Microbiology of the food chain — Whole genome sequencing for typing and genomic characterization of bacteria — General requirements and guidance
- 5) ISO 20397-2:2021. Biotechnology — Massively parallel sequencing - Part 2: Quality evaluation of sequencing data.
- 6) ISO 16140-6: 2019. Microbiology of the food chain - Method validation - Part 6: Protocol for the validation of alternative (proprietary) methods for microbiological confirmation and typing procedures.
- 7) ISO 16140-7:2024. Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation - Part 7: Protocol for the validation of identification methods of microorganisms.

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Annex 1

Acceptance criteria suggested by the different EURLs for the respective pathogens.

Campylobacter jejuni and C. coli

Determination	Sensitivity	Specificity
Species	100%	100%
Sequence type (ST, result of MLST)	100%	100%

Escherichia coli

Determination	Sensitivity	Specificity
<i>stx1, stx2, eae</i> genes	100%	100%
Additional virulence genes	>95%	100%
O antigen*	>95%	100%
H antigen*	>95%	>95%
Sequence type (ST, result of MLST)*	>95%	>95%
<i>stx</i> subtype*	>70%	>70%

* For the O antigen (serogroup), the H antigen, the sequence type (ST), and the *stx* subtype, sensitivity can be calculated globally, whereas specificity can be determined for each individual characteristic (e.g. individual serogroups or H antigens)

Listeria monocytogenes

Determination	Sensitivity	Specificity
Species	100%	100%
Serotype	100%	100%
Sequence type (ST, result of MLST)	100%	100%

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Salmonella enterica

Remark: The validation of WGS serotyping is not part of this document. For this, the procedure described in ISO 16140-6:2019 (6) shall be followed. For in-house validation, only the method comparison study described in clause 6 of ISO 16140-6:2019 (6) has to be followed.

Criteria when comparing WGS results found by a laboratory with reference genomes of the same strains.

	Sensitivity	Specificity
O antigens	>95%	100%
H antigens	>95%	100%
Sequence type (ST, result of MLST)	100%	100%